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2 **NON-SELECTIVE AND TIME-DEPENDENT BEHAVIOURAL RESPONSES**
3 **OF COMMON TOADS (*Bufo bufo*) TO PREDATOR ACOUSTIC CUES**
4

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27 **Abstract**

28 Acoustic predator recognition has rarely been studied in anurans, in spite of the fact that
29 hearing is widespread in these animals, and that it has been demonstrated to play an
30 important role in both arthropods and other vertebrates. Using field playback
31 experiments, we tested the hypothesis that adult common toads (*Bufo bufo*) are capable
32 of recognizing natural vocalizations of a common predator, the Eurasian otter (*Lutra*
33 *lutra*), showing antipredator responses. We found that toads exposed to both natural
34 (two types of otter sounds) and synthetic stimuli (white noise and otter sound-based
35 amplitude modulated white noise) increased time allocated to locomotion and escape
36 behaviour. These responses were correlated with time elapsed from sunset to the onset
37 of testing, and were independent from the type of acoustic signal, toad features and
38 other environmental factors monitored. We conclude that *Bufo bufo* has not developed
39 an selective recognition of predator vocalizations, suggesting that low-frequency or
40 seismic sounds associated with predator movements may provide anurans better cues of
41 an approaching risk. We propose that the time-dependent response to acoustic stimuli of
42 common toads represents a case of threat-sensitivity, and demonstrates that it can occur
43 even when the response to the threat is not predator-specific.

44

45 **Introduction**

46 Eavesdropping on acoustic cues is widespread in animals, and it plays an important role
47 in predatory risk detection (Marler 1967; Simmons et al. 2003). Animal sounds are
48 often produced to communicate information to intended receivers, but they can also be
49 cues to eavesdropping receivers to whom they unintentionally provide useful
50 information. Sounds can propagate quickly and multidirectionally over long distances,
51 so they are often detected sooner than visual cues (Rosenthal & Ryan 2000), and hence

52 they give prey an early warning to evade approaching predators. Furthermore, acoustic
53 cues usually provide reliable information about the location, body size or activity level
54 of the predator (Swaigood et al. 1999; Rosenthal & Ryan 2000; Simmons et al. 2003),
55 and vigilance efforts are not required to detect them. Thereby, effective recognition of
56 sounds associated with predators (biosonar waves, animal vocalizations or incidental
57 noises) or of alarmed conspecifics, even heterospecifics, (mobbing, distress or alarm
58 calls) can increase survival probability. Hence, it is not surprising that sound cues are
59 important in predator detection in many arthropods and vertebrates with auditory
60 abilities (e.g., *spiders*, Lohrey et al. 2009; *insects*, Roeder & Treat 1961; Fenton &
61 Fullard 1981; Faure & Hoy 2000; Jones et al. 2002; Greenfield & Brake 2003; Skals et
62 al. 2005; Barber & Conner 2006; *fish*, Luczukovich 2000; Remage-Healy et al. 2006;
63 *birds*, Hauser & Wrangham 1990; Hauser & Caffrey 1994; Mougeot & Bretagnolle
64 2000; Rattenborg et al. 1999; and *mammals*, Hauser & Wrangham 1990; Macedonia et
65 al. 1991; Noë & Bshary 1997; Hendrie et al. 1998; Eilam et al. 1999; Deecke et al.
66 2002; Swaigood et al. 2003; Baxter et al. 2006; Fichtel 2007).

67 While hearing is an important and well-studied sensory modality in anurans (Narins
68 et al. 2005), acoustic detection of predators has rarely been studied in this group. The
69 few studies available have focused on the predator's role (e.g., how anurans or anurans-
70 eating predators use acoustic cues or water surface waves to detect prey, Jaeger 1976;
71 Tuttle & Ryan 1981; Ryan et al. 1982; Behrend et al. 2006). Little is known about
72 whether anurans can detect potential predators acoustically, but in recent years this issue
73 has attracted increasing attention (Schwartz et al. 2000; Bernal et al. 2007). For
74 example, Grafe et al. (2002) demonstrated that an African anuran (*Hyperolius nitidulus*
75 Peters, 1875) identifies, and subsequently flees, the sound of fire, but only during the
76 short window of time when fire occurs most frequently in the West African savannah.

77 To our knowledge, the present study is the first experiment of acoustic predator
78 recognition to be reported for palearctic anurans.

79 The predator-prey interaction between the Eurasian otter *Lutra lutra* (Linnaeus,
80 1758) and the common toad *Bufo bufo* (Linnaeus, 1758) is a suitable model to study
81 audition in anuran antipredator behaviour. The Eurasian otter is a common seasonal
82 predator of *Bufo bufo* in many Mediterranean habitats (Adrian & Delibes 1987; Lizana
83 & Pérez Mellado 1990; Ruiz-Olmo & Palazón 1997; Clavero et al. 2005), and abundant
84 literature has described its foraging and hunting behaviour (e.g. Mason & MacDonald
85 1986; Kruuk 1995). On land, Eurasian otters often produce vocalizations and noises that
86 can be detected by their prey. Eurasian otters are very vocal mammals and they have a
87 large repertoire of vocalizations (Gnoli & Prigioni 1995; Gnoli et al. 1997; Kruuk
88 2006). While hunting in a group, otters often emit contact whistles to keep the group
89 together, and they commonly caterwaul and hiss during struggles for prey. In addition,
90 when searching for prey otters typically turn over stones and plants on the shore, and
91 thereby they produce airborne sounds and seismic vibrations. To avoid toxins, otters
92 consuming common toads eat only the hind legs or else skin the toad before eating it
93 (Slater 2002). Hence, the remains of toads eaten by otters can be found on shores,
94 making it easy to identify populations where these predation events occur frequently.

95 *Bufo bufo* is one of the most studied, common and widespread anurans in the
96 Palearctic region (e.g. Borkin & Veith 1997). Common toads use acoustic signals for
97 intraspecific communication (Höglund & Robertson 1988; Schneider & Sinsch 2004),
98 and their range of hearing overlaps with the first emphasized harmonics of otter
99 vocalizations (Walkowiak et al. 1981). Male common toads usually remain in spawning
100 sites more than fifteen days, spending several hours per day standing still on the water
101 to defend their territories and acquire mates (Reading & Clarke 1983). This behaviour

102 allows playback tests to be carried out that meet the basic requirements of a stimulus-
103 response experiment (e.g., the exposure time to control and stimuli treatments can be
104 standardized, measurable changes in behaviour can be detected, etc.; McGregor 1992).
105 Common toads attempt to escape from an approaching danger by alternating running
106 and jumping along their escape path. Facing a visible potential predator, toads exhibit a
107 defensive display with their body lifted on straight legs and the head lowered down
108 (García-París et al. 2004).

109 Here, we test the hypothesis that common toads *Bufo bufo* have evolved an acoustic
110 recognition mechanism for detecting the vocalizations of a predator, the Eurasian otter
111 *Lutra lutra*, and respond to them by changing their locomotor behaviour. Using
112 playback experiments under natural field conditions, we measured how behavioural
113 responses of common toads subjected to acoustic stimulation varied as a function of
114 sound type (two otter vocalizations and two synthetic control signals). In addition to
115 testing the ability of *Bufo bufo* to detect *Lutra lutra* acoustically, we investigated which
116 components of the sound (the amplitude envelope alone or the full otter vocalization,
117 including its spectral structure) were likely used by toads as cues. Finally, we studied
118 whether biotic (sex, body size, etc.) and abiotic factors (water temperature, time of
119 night, etc.) could modulate the antipredator responsiveness, selectivity, or both of toads
120 to this acoustic stimulation.

121

122 **Methods**

123 **Study Sites**

124 The playback experiments were conducted during July 2008 and June and July 2009 in
125 two montane lakes in the northwest of the Iberian peninsula (Lago de la Cueva, 43° 03'
126 14" N, 06° 06' 18" W; Lago del Valle, 43° 02' 41" N, 06° 08' 14" W, Somiedo Natural

127 Park, Asturias, Spain). In both populations we have observed otters preying on common
128 toads during the months of May to July. Adults toads were located on the shore of the
129 lakes during the breeding period, where they typically stand still for many hours with
130 most of their body submerged, and only their heads emerging. Behavioural responses of
131 the subjects were studied at night between 00:00 and 06:00 h. Terrestrial habitat (alpine
132 grassland, rock outcrops), altitude (1589 and 1572 m.a.s.l., respectively) and lake
133 perimeter (1.2 and 1.9 km) were similar in the two locations.

134

135 **Stimuli Preparation**

136 Four 8-minute long recordings were used as stimuli in the playbacks: (1) white noise
137 (WN), commonly used in playback design (McGregor 1992), as a control treatment to
138 measure the effect of a random frequency sound; (2) a recording of cries and throat
139 sounds from two Eurasian adult otters during a struggle for food (OT1); (3) a series of
140 contact whistles recorded from a otter family group (OT2); and (4) a synthetic signal
141 composed of the OT2 envelope and WN spectral structure (ENV). This last stimulus
142 was included to identify which components of the otter vocalization (temporal pattern
143 or spectral structure) might cause the toads to react. Otter recordings were obtained
144 from the Fonoteca Zoológica (Research Sound Collection, MNCN-CSIC, Spain; Roché
145 et al. 2005). WN was synthesized at a sample rate of 44.1 kHz and 16-bit resolution
146 (passband 0-22.05 kHz) with Audacity 1.2.6 software, and sound editing was executed
147 with BIAS Peak 4.0 software. Temporal and spectral features of the four stimuli are
148 shown in Fig. 1.

149 The 8-min OT1 and OT2 stimuli were constructed as follows. A fragment of 8.5
150 seconds of peak-normalized vocalizations with their natural intervals was selected for
151 each otter stimulus. This fragment was repeated seven times to create a stimulus 1 min

152 in length. The first 4 repetitions were presented in order of increasing intensity 62, 68,
153 74, 80 dB RMS SPL (fast weighting scale, linear frequency weighting) measured at the
154 position of the toad to simulate the sound coming from an approaching predator. The
155 last 3 repetitions were presented at constant intensity (86 dB RMS SPL, fast weighting
156 scale, linear frequency weighting) to simulate the predator foraging in close proximity
157 to the subject. This 1 min sequence, followed by a 24 s long interval of silence, was
158 repeated six times to mimic a series of approaches of the otter searching for its prey. We
159 replicated the whole 8-min sequence for WN and for ENV.

160

161 **Instrumentation and Experimental Procedure**

162 The stimuli were played back with a laptop Apple iBook PPC G4 and amplified through
163 a custom-made sound amplifier with a fine adjustment of the output level. The synthetic
164 and otter stimuli were broadcast through a loudspeaker Dynaudio BM5 (frequency
165 response: 50-21000 Hz). A 20 meter extension cable was used to maximize the distance
166 between the audio-setup from the subject. To avoid visual interference, a black fabric
167 screen was placed covering the equipment. Before each playback test, each stimulus
168 was adjusted to the same sound pressure level, as measured at 1 m with a sound meter
169 (fast weighting scale, linear frequency weighting, Brüel & Kjær 2238 Mediator). The
170 loudspeaker was positioned 1.0-1.2 m in front of the experimental subject. During its
171 placement, special care was taken to avoid disturbance. The playback test was initiated
172 1 min after placing the speaker.

173 A single test with only one stimulus was conducted for each subject. The four
174 stimuli were presented randomly to the toads in each night. Behaviour was measured 8
175 min before stimulus presentation, 8 min during stimulus presentation and 8 min after
176 stimulus presentation. For each test period, we recorded time allocated to the four most

177 common behaviours: (1) *standing*, toads remaining still on the water; (2) *locomoting*,
178 toads moving to another location at the lake shore; (3) *defending*, toads making a
179 defensive display; (4) *escaping*, toads leaving the water completely, using the typical
180 alarm display of walking fast or jumping toward a refuge. In addition, for toads that
181 escaped or locomoted, we used a laser distancemeter (Leica DISTO Classic5) to
182 estimate total distance moved and displacement angle relative to the loudspeaker.

183 Air and water temperature, and relative humidity were monitored every 5 min by
184 dataloggers (HOBO Pendant G, HOBO Pro-V2). Toad sex, body size, measures as
185 snout to vent length (SVL), and cloacal temperature were recorded from each toad at the
186 end of the playback test. Background noise at the test position was also measured after
187 the experiments. Background noise was measured when wind was not blowing. To
188 avoid retesting the same individuals, the two study sites were divided into sectors. Each
189 sector was used only one night for the playbacks, and subjects were marked by a
190 subcutaneous injection of alcian blue in the ventral face of one limb.

191

192 **Data Analysis**

193 The pre-stimulus period was used as a baseline to compare with behaviour during and
194 after stimuli exposure. Initially, non-parametric equivalents of repeated-measures
195 ANOVAs were computed to test for differences among test periods (pre-stimulus,
196 stimulus and post-stimulus) in time allocated to each behaviour. The next analyses were
197 used to test for stimulus effects independent of baseline allocations to standing,
198 locomoting, defending and escaping. First, the baseline allocations to each of those
199 behaviours was subtracted from the time allocations during the stimulus and post-
200 stimulus periods, and then these baseline adjusted allocations were compared with
201 Kruskal-Wallis tests.

202 In addition, we tested the effects of eight variables on the probability that toads
203 responded by escaping (coded as 1) or not escaping (coded as 0) during any of the four
204 stimuli presentation. We used binomial logistic regression with forward stepwise
205 selection as a function of eight biotic or abiotic factors (air temperature, water
206 temperature, relative humidity and time elapsed from sunset to the onset of the
207 experiment; moon phase –from 0 % in new moon night to 100 % in full moon night–;
208 and toad sex, body size and cloacal temperature after experiment) that we hypothesized
209 might affect the decision to escape. Baseline rates were not included in the regression
210 model because escape behaviour was completely absent in the pre-stimulus period (Fig.
211 2). Because males (n=56) and females (n=13) did not respond significantly different
212 according to this model (GLM z-Score=0.344, p=0.557), their responses were pooled
213 for analysis. Kruskal Wallis and Mann-Whitney *U* tests were also conducted to compare
214 total distance locomoted and displacement angle for locomoting behaviour with total
215 distance locomoted and displacement angle for escaping behaviour. All statistics and
216 graphs were computed using *R* (R Development Core Team 2008).

217

218 **Results**

219 Behavioural responses were recorded for 69 toads exposed to a single stimulus each.
220 The data were collected over the course of 18 nights. Defensive behaviour was not
221 observed during any period. Time allocated to each of the other three behaviours
222 differed significantly across the pre-stimulus, stimulus and post-stimulus periods, as
223 reflected by Friedman's test (standing, $\chi^2=40.5$, $p<0.001$; locomoting, $\chi^2=16.5$,
224 $p<0.001$; escaping, $\chi^2=24.0$, $p<0.001$; $df=2$ for all tests). In addition, post-hoc Wilcoxon
225 tests were significant ($p<0.005$) for all comparisons across periods except for the
226 stimulus and post-stimulus periods comparison of time allocated to locomoting ($Z=-$

227 1.25, $p=0.212$). Common toads responded to sounds by increasing locomoting and
228 escaping, and standing was reduced (Fig. 2). Nevertheless, Kruskal-Wallis tests
229 revealed that those changes, independent of baseline, were not significantly different
230 between stimuli, neither during stimulus presentation (standing, $K=3.46$, $p=0.326$;
231 locomoting, $K=0.73$, $p=0.867$; escaping, $K=1.61$, $p=0.658$; $df=3$ for all tests) nor post-
232 stimulus (standing, $K=4.90$, $p=0.180$; locomoting, $K=3.65$, $p=0.301$; escaping, $K=1.14$,
233 $p=0.678$; $df=3$ for all tests). These results suggest that common toads were affected by
234 stimuli exposure, but in the same way by each stimulus (non-selective response).

235 Standing was the most common behaviour during all periods. Escaping (recorded in
236 17 % ($n=12$) of the toads) was less frequent than locomoting. Escape responses took
237 place only during acoustic stimulation, never during the pre-stimulus period, and they
238 were triggered by each of the treatments, even WN (Fig. 2). The logistic regression used
239 to model the *presence-absence of escape behaviour during the stimulus period* revealed
240 that the escape responses were strongly influenced by time elapsed since sunset
241 ($p=0.001$). Time elapsed from sunset to the onset of the stimulus presentation was the
242 only predictor variable selected by the forward selection procedure, and it explained
243 69.2 % of the probability of escape response. None of the toads exposed to a stimulus
244 before 345 min after sunset ($n=55$) showed escape behaviour, while 80 % of them tested
245 after that hour did (Fig. 3). The regression function was $y=1/1+e^{-(13.98 + (-0.038 \times X))}$, where
246 X is minutes from sunset at the onset of the playback. A similar pattern was not found in
247 the pre-stimulus period because no individuals exhibited escape behaviour before
248 stimulus presentation. These results point out that escape responses were time-
249 dependent and acoustically mediated, and they were not caused simply by natural
250 periodicity of activity in toads. At the time of the end of the experiments most non-
251 tested toads remained in the water.

252 Toads that exhibited escape behaviour travelled greater distances than toads that
253 locomoted during the stimulus period (Mann-Whitney U test; $Z=-3.39$, $p=0.001$), but
254 again there was no effect of the stimulus type ($K=2.04$, $p=0.564$, $df=3$). Toads escaped
255 over long distances, usually covering more than 10 m by the end of the playback. Toads
256 typically escaped by moving toward the hillsides. The angle between the loudspeaker
257 and the direction toads moved varied slightly between locomoting ($64 \pm 53^\circ$, range 0-
258 180°) and escape ($58 \pm 32^\circ$, range 0- 105°), but these angles did not differ significantly
259 between behaviours (Mann-Whitney U test; $Z=-0.28$, $p=0.782$) or stimuli ($K=2.67$,
260 $p=0.444$, $df=3$). The background noise at the subject position after the playbacks
261 averaged 36.7 dB RMS SPL (range 21.0-57.1; fast weighting scale, linear frequency
262 weighting), always under the SPL of the stimuli.

263

264 **Discussion**

265 The results of the playback tests clearly indicate an absence of otter vocal
266 recognition in *Bufo bufo*. The similar responses to the different types of stimulus
267 confirms that the toads were not able to assess efficiently the potential risk from the
268 acoustic cues, in spite of the large acoustic differences among the otter vocalizations
269 and the synthetic noises. If we consider these results together with other recently
270 published reports, it appears that predator vocalization recognition is not widespread in
271 anurans. Schwartz et al. (2000) found that both male calling and female choice of *Hyla*
272 *versicolor* LeConte, 1825 remained unchanged in presence of calls by the anuran
273 predator *Lithobates catesbeianus* (Shaw, 1802). Similar results have been reported by
274 Bernal et al. (2007) for females and males of *Engystomops pustulosus* (Cope, 1864) that
275 were exposed to predator calls of *Leptodactylus pentadactylus* (Laurenti, 1768). Other
276 non-anuran prey organisms, such as squid, kangaroos or mice, also fail to recognize

277 predators when exposed to acoustic signals of both echolocating and non-echolocating
278 predators (Wilson et al. 2007; Blumstein et al. 2000; Hendrie et al. 1998; Eilam et al.
279 1999). The reasons for the lack of predator recognition (i.e., lack of acoustic selectivity)
280 in these specific examples are still not clear.

281 In common toads, we suggest that the natural selection derived from otter predation
282 has probably not been sufficiently strong or prolonged to favour an acoustic recognition
283 mechanism for otter vocalizations. The non-selective behavioural responses of toads to
284 otter vocal cues are consistent with the idea that the hearing sensitivity of common
285 toads is not properly tuned to otter vocalizations. Although the hearing range of *Bufo*
286 *bufo* (0.1-3.0 kHz; Walkowiak et al. 1981) includes the lower emphasized harmonics of
287 the otter vocalizations, most spectral components of these sounds (1.5-9.0 kHz) are
288 above the common toads' hearing threshold. Thus, we hypothesize that when anurans
289 assess predatory risk, low-frequency or seismic sounds associated with predator
290 movements may play a more important role than predator vocalizations. Bernal et al.
291 (2007) described changes of *Engystomops pustulosus* female preferences and/or male
292 calling in response to low-frequency noises associated with predation risk (bat wing-
293 beats, leaf rustles and water splash). In addition, a strong escape response has been
294 found in the African anuran *Hyperolius nitidulus* that fled from noise of fire, whose
295 spectral peak is below 300 Hz (Grafe et al. 2002). Neuroethological studies have also
296 suggested that the low-frequency hearing sensitivity recorded in the auditory tuning
297 curves of Bufonidae and other anurans (which are not tuned to conspecific mating calls)
298 may correspond with biological phenomena, such as predator detection, among others
299 (Walkowiak et al. 1981; Narins et al. 2005).

300 Our results showed that, despite the absence of otter vocal recognition, acoustic
301 disruptions can elicit antipredator behaviour in *Bufo bufo*, when these disruptions are

302 presented in the last hours of the night. Each of the stimuli triggered escape responses,
303 but these responses were strongly time-dependent. We suggest that this strategy
304 represents a form of threat-sensitivity (Helfman 1989). According to the hypothesis that
305 predator avoidance is threat-sensitive, the responses of prey are modulated by their
306 assessment of predatory risk and the relevance of other simultaneous activities. This
307 hypothesis suggests that there is an adaptative trade-off mechanism that reduces the
308 costs of triggering antipredator responses. The threat-sensitivity in common toads was
309 related to the time when the threat was made, but not to the magnitude of the threat,
310 since their responses were not influenced by the sound type. We suggest that subjects
311 altered their avoidance responses during the course of the night in a manner that reflects
312 the relevance of other activities in which they were involved. During the first hours of
313 the night, in response to acoustic disruption common toads may have avoided leaving
314 the lake and reacting with antipredator behaviour because they were involved in other
315 activities, such as territorial defense and mate acquisition. The cost of triggering escape
316 behaviour during this period would be high and might only be acceptable if the toad
317 detected an unambiguous sign that a predator was present. In contrast, during the last
318 hours of the night, other potential activities of common toads were likely to be less
319 critical, so they left the lake in response of any acoustic disruption. Therefore, we
320 suggest that these time-dependent responses recorded in *Bufo bufo* might be caused by a
321 change in the tolerance of common toads to acoustic disruptions related to a decrease of
322 their investment in other activities. Future studies should test this hypothesis. In any
323 event, given that the responses of individuals were time-dependent and non-selective,
324 our results show that threat-sensitivity can occur in prey even when the response to the
325 threat is not predator-specific.

326 In mammals and arthropods, the main factors that have been shown to modify

327 responses to predator acoustic cues are amplitude and other features of the signal
328 (Swaigood et al. 1999; Faure & Hoy 2000; Greenfield & Brake 2003; Stankowich &
329 Blumstein 2005), ongoing parental care (Swaigood et al. 2003), habituation to the
330 signal (Deecke et al. 2002; Macedonia et al. 1991), and concurrence of other sensory
331 cues, such as chemical or visual cues (Skals et al. 2005; Lohrey et al. 2009). To our
332 knowledge, this study is the first to demonstrate the influence of circadian cycle on
333 antipredator responses of anurans to acoustic cues.

334

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347

348 **Fig. 1:** Oscillograms (top), spectrograms (middle) and power spectra (bottom) of a
 349 fragment of the four stimuli used for playback tests: WN (white noise), OT1 (cries and
 350 throat sounds of the Eurasian otter), OT2 (contact whistles of the Eurasian otter), and
 351 ENV (envelope of OT2 with spectral structure of WN). Power spectra analysis
 352 bandwidth: 20 Hz; frame overlap: 90.

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356

357 **Fig. 2:** Mean (\pm 95 % C.I.) of the percentage time allocated to *standing* (a), *locomoting*
 358 (b) and *escaping* (c) of 69 common toads (*Bufo bufo*) before (pre-stimulus, 8 min),
 359 during (stimulus, 8 min), and after (post-stimulus, 8 min) the exposure of one of four
 360 acoustic stimuli: white noise, WN (white bars, n=16); OT1 (striped bars, n=21); OT2
 361 (gray bars, n=16); and ENV (black bars, n=16).

362

363

364

365 **Fig. 3:** Probability function of escape response according to time elapsed from sunset to
 366 the onset of the playback (binomial regression model, 69.2% deviance, $p=0.001$). Black
 367 points: subjects which showed escape behaviour; white points: subjects which did not.

368

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